

Nasca Culture Religion

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Entry tags: Nasca Religion, Pre-Inka Religions, Peru, Nasca Religion, Religious Group, Language, Unknown, South American Religions

On the southern coast of Peru, the extent of the influence of the Nasca culture (Early Intermediate Period - EIP) has been located as far north as the Chincha Valley and the Acarí Valley to the south. This cultural unit which was governed by a centralized Nasca authority from the Rio Grande Basin (Canziani, 2012; Carmichael, 2020), follows relative chronology with a high diversity of ceramic styles 1-8/9 (see Uhle in Kroeber, 1924; Rowe, 1960; Menzel, 1971; among others) and the absolute dates of many projects such as Cahuachi (Orefici, 2012), Palpa (Unkel et al. 2007), etc. that refine the chronology for three periods: early, middle and late Nasca (Conlee, 2010).

Date Range: 100 CE - 800 CE

Region: Nasca extent of influence

Region tags: Peru

From the EIP, this area has been located as far north as the Chincha Valley and the Acarí Valley to the south. However, to the MH with Nasca phases 8-9 pottery style, the influence area has been placed in the Cañete Valley and Ayacucho region (see Fernandini, 2015; Olivera et al. 2008)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Fuente 1: Pardo, C. y Fux, P. (2017). NASCA. Museo de Arte de Lima - MALI
- Fuente 2: Orefici, F. (2019). Cultura alimentaria de los antiguos Nasca. Universidad San Martin de Porres
- Fuente 3: Schreiber, K. y Lancho, J. (2006). Aguas En El Desierto. Los Puquios De Nasca. Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú
- Fuente 1: Herran, E. (2018). LÍNEAS DE NASCA. DE LOS HOMBRES QUE DIBUJARON EN EL DESIERTO. Universidad San Martin de Porres
- Fuente 2: Beresford-Jones, D. (2014). Los bosques desaparecidos de la antigua Nazca Estudio de un caso de colapso ecológico y cultural.
- Fuente 3: Silverman, H. (2002). The Nasca. Blackwell Pub
- Fuente 1: Uhle, M. (1914). The Nazca Pottery of Ancient Peru
- Fuente 2: Proulx, D. (1990). NASCA ICONOGRAPHY. Inca - Perú: 3000 Ans d'Histoire, edited by Sergio Purin, Pp. 384-399. Gent (Belgium): Imschoot, uitgevers.

– Fuente 3: Carmichael, Patrick (1994) "The Life from Death Continuum in Nasca Imagery," *Andean Past*: Vol. 4 , Article 9.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– URL de la Fuente 1:

https://people.umass.edu/proulx/online_pubs/Nasca_Ceramic_Iconography_Overview.pdf

– Descripción de la Fuente 1: Proulx, D. (s.f.). *Nasca Ceramic Iconography: An Overview*. (Reprinted from) *The Studio Potter* 29(1):37-43

– URL de la Fuente 2: <https://repositorio.pucp.edu.pe/index/bitstream/handle/123456789/114041/9916-Texto%20del%20art%C3%ADculo-39247-1-10-20140802.pdf?sequence=2>

– Descripción de la Fuente 2: Klokoeník, J., Vitek, F., Klokoeníkova, Z. y Rodriguez, A. (2002). LOS GEOGLIFOS DE NAZCA, PERÚ. *BIRA* 29, 13-29.

– URL de la Fuente 3: https://espacio.fundaciontelefonica.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/guia_practica_Nasca.pdf

– Descripción de la Fuente 3: Fundación Telefónica. (s.f). *NASCA BUSCANDO HUELLAS EN EL DESIERTO*

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– URL de la Fuente 1: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-319-47052-8>

– Descripción de la Fuente 1: Rosa Lasaponara, Nicola Masini, Giuseppe Orefici (Eds.). (2016). *The Ancient Nasca World. New Insights from Science and Archaeology*

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Sí

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Sí

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Sí

Notes: Likely yes, there are many Nazca Head-hunters and Trophy Heads

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Sí

Notes: Likely yes, there are many Nazca Head-hunters and Trophy Heads

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religion have official political support

– Sí

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Sí

Notes: Religion and the political system were at the same level, and could be a single system, at the moment it is not clear. However, there is a certain redistribution of assets to maintain religious events

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Sí

Notes: The political-religious system assumes the cost to build and maintain buildings, feeding people and providing raw materials.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Sí

Notes: Likely yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Sí

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Sí

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– El campo lo desconoce

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– El campo lo desconoce

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Sí

Notes: Cahuachi is the main archaeological site of Nasca, this building was a space of habitat and continuous management of the Nazca elites

Reference: Gavazzi, Adine. “La Arquitectura De Cahuachi”. In *Nasca - El Desierto De Los Dioses De Cahuachi*, 112-309, 2009.

Reference: BACHIR, AÏCHA, and ÓSCAR LLANOS. “El Gran Templo Del Centro Ceremonial De Cahuachi (nazca, Perú)”. *DIMENSIÓN ANTROPOLÓGICA* 38 (2006): 49-89.

https://www.dimensionantropologica.inah.gob.mx/pdf/dian_38_02.pdf.

Reference: Orefici, Giuseppe. *Cahuachi Capital Teocrática Nasca*. Universidad de San Martín de Porres, 2012.

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. *NASCA*. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Metros cuadrados: 24000000

Reference: BACHIR, AÏCHA, and ÓSCAR LLANOS. "El Gran Templo Del Centro Ceremonial De Cahuachi (nazca, Perú)". DIMENSIÓN ANTROPOLÓGICA 38 (2006): 49-89.
https://www.dimensionantropologica.inah.gob.mx/pdf/dian_38_02.pdf.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Altura, en metros: 28

Notes: The ceremonial building or "Gran pirámide"

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Sí

↳ Tombs:

– Sí

Reference: De La Torre, Juan. "De Entierros Y Ofrendas: Un Cementerio En Tiempos Nasca, En El Valle De Aja, Perú". *Arqueología Y Sociedad* 25 (2013): 89-114.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Sí

↳ Temples:

– Sí

Reference: Orefici, Giuseppe. *Cahuachi Capital Teocrática Nasca*. Universidad de San Martín de

Reference: Orlandi, Giuseppe. "Carandén Capital (cerámica Nasca)." Universidad de San Martín de Porres, 2012.

↳ Altars:

– Sí

Reference: Reindel, Markus, Johny Isla, and Karsten Lambers. "Altares En El Desierto: Las Estructuras De Piedra Sobre Los Geoglifos Nasca En Palpa". *Arqueología Y Sociedad*, no. 17 (April 23, 2017): 179–222. <https://doi.org/10.15381/arqueolsoc.2006n17.e13140>.

↳ Devotional markers:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Sí

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Sí (especifique): kochas, puquios-acueductos

Is iconography present:

– Sí

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– En algunos espacios públicos

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Sí

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Sí

Notes: In pottery

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Sí

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. *NASCA*. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Sí

Notes: Nasca Geoglyphs and petroglyphs

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Sí

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Sí

Notes: The Nazca ceramics reflect a kind of "horror of emptiness". They covered with complex representations of animals, supernatural beings, human beings and many abstracts simbols such as stars, points and geometric figures

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Sí

Notes: Related to trophy heads

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Sí

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Sí

Notes: Music, sacrifices, plants, warriors, combat warriors, economic activities such as fishing, hunting and farming

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Sí

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Sí

Are pilgrimages present:

– Sí

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– El campo lo desconoce

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– El campo lo desconoce

Belief in afterlife:

– Sí

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Sí

Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Sí

Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Sí

Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Sí

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Sí

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Sí

Reference: Valdez, Lidio. "Conflicto Y Decapitación Humana En Amato (valle De Acarí, Perú)". *Bulletin De L'institut Français D'études Andines* 2 (2009): 177-204.
<https://doi.org/10.4000/bifea.2666>.

Reference: Verano, John. "Mummified Trophy Heads from Peru: Diagnostic Features and Medicolegal Significance". *Journal of Forensic Sciences* 48 (2003): JFS2002307.

↳ Interment:

– Sí

Reference: De La Torre, Juan. "De Entierros Y Ofrendas: Un Cementerio En Tiempos Nasca, En El Valle De Aja, Perú". *Arqueología Y Sociedad* 25 (2013): 89-114.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Sí

↳ Cannibalism:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Feeding to animals:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Sí

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Sí

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Sí

Are grave goods present:

– Sí

↳ Personal effects:

– Sí

↳ Valuable items:

– Sí

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Sí

Notes: Some metal artifacts with antropomorphic iconography or fine textiles for funeral bundles

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Sí

Notes: Pottery, textile, finely crafted wooden artifacts

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Other grave goods:

– Sí

Are formal burials present:

– Sí

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Sí

Notes: Nazca culture has specific places as cementeries

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Sí

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Sí

Notes: Nazca religion was politeist but they have a principal god named Kon (rain god), who was a deity to the Paracas culture (Formative or Early Horizon), then adopted by Nazca culture (Early Intermediate period) until the Incas (Late Horizon period)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Sí (especifique): Rain God

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Sí

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Sí
 - Notes: In cermaic, textile wood or metal iconography

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Sí
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
 - Sí
 - Notes: In pottery, textile wood or metal iconography
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Sí
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Sí
 - Notes: In all Indian religion, certain gods have relevance and are represented more frequently than others
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Sí
 - Notes: They are related to nature (rain, water, sun, etc.)
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– El campo lo desconoce

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Sí

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Archaeologists have not found material evidence to confirm, so any religious requirement to be part of the group is unknown but not ruled out

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It is not known if to "belong" they had to sacrifice an individual, but to appease natural phenomena people were offered.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It is not known if to "belong" they had to sacrifice an individual, but to appease natural phenomena people were offered. Like capacochas (Inca rituals)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Sí

Notes: Due to the architecture, certain spaces are designated for social gatherings of a religious nature.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Sí

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Sí

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– El campo lo desconoce

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Sí

Notes: hallucinogens (San Pedro cactus)

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Sí

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Circumcision:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Food taboos:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Hair:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Dress:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Ornaments:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Other:
– Sí (especifique): cranial deformities

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:
– El campo lo desconoce

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):
– Una sociedad de jefatura

Notes: Nazca society was organized in a hierarchical and stratified manner, with a ruling elite at the top of the social structure. There were different groups of people with their own elites and social classes, estimating an organization of local chieftaincies or "señores locales".

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:
– Sí

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:
– El campo lo desconoce

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Sí

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Sí

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– El campo lo desconoce

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Sí

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Sí

Notes: Puquios, acueductos Nazca

Reference: Schreiber , Katharina. "The Puquios of Nasca". *Latin American Antiquity* 6 (1995): 229–54.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Sí

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Maybe not as "taxes" but the production of certain items for the elite and religious events was commissioned.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Likely yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Likely yes, but researchers do not have many information about it, they can also stimulate bellic actions within the warrior scenes in pottery or in broken bones (burials)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Archaeologists have found no evidence of any kind of writing

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Probablemente sí, siguiendo las teorías de Kosok y Reich sobre las Líneas de Nazca son una especie de calendario astronómico pero algunos argumentan que este podría estar equivocado.

Reference: Klokoeník, Jaroslav, Frantisek Vitek, Zuzana Klokoeníková, and Aurelio Rodriguez. "LOS GEOGLIFOS DE NAZCA, PERÚ". BIRA 29 (2002): 13-29.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Sí

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Caza (incluyendo animales marinos)

– Pesca

– Agricultura a gran escala (ej. monocultivos, sistemas de irrigación organizados)

Reference: Pardo, Cecilia, and Peter Fux, eds.. NASCA. Edited by Cecilia Pardo and Peter Fux. Lima, Perú: MALI, 2017.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: In the Andes the elite held political, religious and cultural power in society. Leaders used religion and the objects associated with it as a way to legitimize their authority and control over society.

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